

MORAL EDUCATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION EXERCISE PARTICIPANTS

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Abstract: This article presents the scientific heritage of the great scholars and thinkers of the Great East in organizing moral education, leading methods of physical exercises used in the spiritual and moral development of the individual, and develops recommendations for the effective use of the possibilities of physical education in educating the moral qualities of students of secondary general education schools.

Keywords: moral education, pedagogy, physical education and sports, professional qualifications, communicativeness, healthy lifestyle, competence, physical development.

INTRODUCTION

It is difficult to overestimate the role of physical education and sports in modern society in matters of spiritual and moral education of young people. They are not only an effective means of physical development of a person, strengthening and protecting his health, a sphere of communication and manifestation of people's social activity, a rational form of organization and spending free time. They, of course, have a great impact on many other aspects of human life: labor activity, reputation and position in society, the formation of moral and intellectual qualities, aesthetic ideals and value orientations. Physical education and sports provide each member of society with the widest opportunities for the development, affirmation and manifestation of their personality.

Science and culture have been developed since ancient times in our country, which connects the East and the West, where great civilizations adjoin. Especially

in the Middle Ages, thousands of scholars, poets, and great thinkers emerged from our native land.

The discoveries of the great scholars and thinkers of the East are the foundation of modern science and development. Any changes, innovations in the development of society, especially processes and discoveries that give a great impetus to the development of humanity, do not happen by themselves. For this, first of all, there must be centuries-old traditions, appropriate conditions, a school of thought, a cultural and spiritual environment. The great enlightener Abdullah Avloni in his work "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" says that ethics is "a science that calls people to goodness and turns them away from evil." It is in this source that the scholar dwells on good and bad behavior, which provides information about morality and its social significance. In the scholar's view, good character traits include: fortitude (intelligence), faith (faith), modesty (purity and cleanliness), zeal, austerity (righteous deeds), contentment, knowledge, patience, discipline, self-control, conscience, love for one's homeland, truthfulness, exemplary behavior, chastity, modesty, understanding and wisdom, economy, dignity (pride), love, and forgiveness. These qualities are considered the main qualities of moral and ethical character. They are based on love and loyalty to the Motherland, a moral attitude to work, a moral approach to those around them, as well as the attitude of each student to himself and his personal behavior.

DISCUSSION

Among the problems that concern humanity in the world, the scale of issues related to immorality is taking a leading place. In the era of globalization and the expansion of the scope of mass culture, the issue of human morality is becoming a global problem. In our country, effective reforms are being implemented in the education system regarding education. This shows that the issue of youth education is one of the important problems facing not only our country, but also the entire

human community. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, drawing attention to the issue of youth education at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, said: "Today's youth in the world is the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, as they number 2 billion people. The future and prosperity of our planet depend on what kind of people our children will become and grow up to be. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to realize their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of violent extremism. For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in the field of social support for the younger generation, protection of its rights and interests." Currently, there is a contradiction between the requirements of society for the formation of youth morality and the insufficient development of a solution to this issue. The possibilities of the educational process in educating students' moral qualities increase as a result of pedagogically correctly organized cognitive interaction and communication of subjects of educational and pedagogical activity in the classroom. The spiritual and moral education of young people, their preparation for independent life is the most important task that must be solved not only by the state, but also by society. The most important thing in the upbringing of a child at school is to organize systematic, pedagogically based independent self-education work, in order to instill in students an understanding of the relationship between a person's behavior and his qualities, a desire to cultivate valuable volitional qualities in themselves, to give students an understanding of how to engage in self-education, and to organize the socially useful activities of adolescents in a way that contributes to upbringing and self-education.

Regular sports training can have a significant impact on the development of skills and personal qualities of students, which are so necessary for them in their future work. First of all, such of them as discipline, dedication, hard work, self-confidence were highlighted. It is important to note that these skills and qualities are included in the list of necessary competencies put forward by employers, which, according to some authors, a modern specialist should have. Physical education and sports, in addition to physical conditioning, contribute to the development of leadership qualities, communication skills, the ability to behave correctly in a team, and readiness for cooperation. This group of students is more characterized by a sense of duty, conscientiousness, and composure. They are able to maintain composure in the most difficult situations, quickly find the right solutions and apply them in practice. However, not all educational institutions in our country pay due attention to the issues of involving young people in active physical education and sports. In some cases, these processes are negatively affected by the underestimation of the role of physical education in the training of future specialists by the heads of educational institutions, as a result - the lack of a decent sports base and quality equipment for sports. In most situations, this is due to the inability, and often the unwillingness to look for new effective forms and methods of attracting students to stadiums and sports grounds in the conditions of modern life. First of all, it is necessary to provide access and create conditions for students to practice the most popular and favorite sports (athletics, martial arts, gymnastics, wrestling, sports games, etc.) at a time convenient for them. Then, give them the opportunity to participate in

interesting competitions, both within educational institutions and in the region, making them real sports holidays.

In the conditions of the modern era, the professional requirements imposed on future teachers are caused by their inability and often unwillingness to search for new effective forms and methods. The formation and development of students' spiritual and moral qualities makes the task of developing optimal psychological support programs for this process urgent. This, in turn, requires the formation of a generation of subject teachers with high personal and professional competence, and requires achieving high quality psychological and pedagogical support. The effectiveness of physical education teachers' activities is largely related to their pedagogical competence. In developed countries of the world, the role of physical culture as a factor in improving a person and society is increasing. A healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports are becoming a unifying force, a national idea that serves the development of a strong state and a healthy society. Accordingly, the requirements placed by society on the quality of training of specialists serving in the field of physical education and sports, and the level of their professional qualifications are increasing. Addressing the person-centered approach to education helps to direct the future physical education teacher towards personal, general cultural development in technological development.

Since the goal of physical education is to optimize the physical development of a person, to improve his physical qualities, along with the upbringing of the spiritual and moral qualities characteristic of a socially active person, educators must ensure that their students are ready for productive work and other activities. The organizational (management) competence of a physical education teacher consists of the ability to organize the educational process, physical education activities of students and the teacher's behavior, as well as to set clear goals for the correct presentation of educational material in the lesson. The teacher's rhetorical competence (culture of speech interaction) is of great importance in ensuring the

effectiveness of educational activities. Increasing the teacher's speech responsibility is one of the necessary conditions for professionalism. It is necessary to pay attention to the effectiveness of the teacher's words, clarity of speech, ability to communicate with parents, and acoustic conditions of the gym. A student's interest in physical education usually arises on the basis of the motives and goals of physical education and sports activities, which are:

- satisfaction with the educational process (emotionality, communication, diversity, etc.);
- lesson results (mastering new knowledge, actions, testing oneself, improving the result);
- success in the classroom (cultivating personal qualities, improving sports skills, strengthening health), etc.

If a student does not have a clear goal in performing physical education and sports activities, he will not show interest. A student's interest in physical education lessons is directly related to purposefulness, accuracy, deep motivation, stability of interests, regularity of classes, organization of competitions, activity and initiative. By conducting diagnostics of moral and volitional development in the educational process, it would be possible to achieve results in improving moral qualities in students. However, it is possible to control the quality of education in the education system, but indicators for assessing the educational process have not been developed. This process is determined mainly not by qualitative indicators, but by quantitative indicators.

CONCLUSION

Effective use of the opportunities of physical education in the formation of moral qualities of students in education is an important factor in the formation and development of many moral qualities in the growing younger generation, such as patience, willpower, hard work, empathy, teamwork, patriotism. In implementing this goal, the training of future physical education teachers as personnel meeting

the requirements of the time should be considered the most important task for higher educational institutions, and it is important for teachers of secondary schools to have professional competence. Every educator-pedagogue, regardless of which subject he is a teacher of, should consider the educational task as a primary task in the lesson process, along with setting an educational task. For this, the educator himself must understand that he must be an example in education. Only then can the educator fully fulfill his task.

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